

Policy Formulation and Implementation at Secondary Level of Education in Nigeria: Challenges and Way Forward

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Abstract

Secondary school level education in Nigeria as enshrined in the national policy on education shall make contributions to national development in the Provision of trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades. This paper reviewed issues such as, Scope and Purpose of Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria's Context, Features of Policy in Education, Sources of Education Policy, Types of Education Policy, Importance of Education Policy, Policy making process, The National Policy on Education, Policy Implementation, Purpose of Policy evaluation, Criteria for evaluating Public Policy, Characteristics of a good education Policy, A brief history of education policies formulation and implementation in Nigeria, and Problems of Policy Implementation in secondary Education in Nigeria, were discussed, The paper concludes that, the failure of educational policies in Nigeria has been traced to poor monitoring and implementation of educational policies the secondary education as enshrined in the national policy on education has stipulated specific goals and objectives which can only be achieved through implementation and evaluation via effective management. The goal attainment may be viewed as a destination, where management represents the vehicle, leadership style represents the fuel and people (government and school administrators) are the (drivers) implementers. It was recommended, Governments should ensure continuity in the implementation of education policies before embarking of formulating new ones More effort should be put to carve the menace of corruption in the implementation of education policies and finally, effective education policies implementation mechanism should be put in place so as to ensure optimal result.

Keywords: Educational Policy, Formulation, Implementation,

Introduction

Secondary Education is one of the bedrocks and the foundation level in Nigerian educational system. As a result of its importance, there is need to effectively and efficiently manage or administer resources (Human and materials) in Secondary Schools in order to realize the laudable Goals and objectives of Secondary Education as enshrined in the National Policy on Education. Secondary Education has been described as the bedrock of every society and tool for nation building. For qualitative education to be achieved in a nation the principal actors of learning who are the teachers, learners and the environment must be cooperatively organized. Secondary Education is described as an instrument per excellent for effecting national development (FRN, 2014). However, realizing the role that education plays in national development, Nigeria government have to venture into various educational policies and programmes with the expectation of meeting the country's needs in the areas of human and infrastructure development. According to the National Policy on Education (2014), Secondary education in Nigeria has the following objectives to:

1. Provide holders of the basic education certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic studies certificate with opportunity for education at a higher level, irrespective of gender, social status and religious or ethnic background.
2. Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the difference in talent, disposition opportunities and future roles.

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3. Provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades.
4. Provide Entrepreneurial, technical and vocational jobs, specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development.
5. Develop and promote Nigerian Languages, art and culture in the contexts of world heritage.
6. Inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence.
7. Foster patriotism, rational writing and security education with the emphasis on the committees in spite of our diversity.
8. Raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour.

According to Jumare (2019) these laudable objectives can only be achieved with the help of several individuals within and also outside the school. However, within the school a number of efforts especially by the school head in relation to the administration of secondary schools.

Scope and Purpose of Secondary Education in Nigeria's Context

Secondary education is provided for children after primary education, that is, before tertiary education. It is aimed at developing a child better than the primary level, because it is obvious that primary education is insufficient for children to acquire literacy, numeracy, and communication skills (Ige, 2011; Yusuf, 2009). Such education is provided in secondary school, which can be owned by government (State or Federal), individuals or community. It is divided into two phases as follows:

Basic level of Education

This is the first three years of secondary education. The curriculum at this level is pre-vocational and academic in scope. Core, pre-vocational and non-prevocational subjects are included in the curriculum. The core subjects include: English Language, Mathematics, French, and a major Nigerian Language other than that of environment. A child has to do the junior school certificate Examination (JSCE), being coordinated by State Ministries of Education or Federal Ministry of Education.

Senior Secondary School Level

This is the next three years after Basic level education. It has wider scope than the Basic level (JS) phase and aims at broadening the knowledge and skills of a student beyond the Basic level and thus prepares him/her for further education. It is academic and vocational in scope. A student has of minimum of seven and maximum of eight subjects, comprising of six core subjects: English Language, Mathematics, a major Nigerian Language, one science, an art, and vocational subject. One or two others elective are to be selected from the art, science, technical, social science, and vocational subject. Certificate at the end of this phase depend on the performance of a student in the continuous assessment (CA) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE), coordinated by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO). A child must obtain a minimum of five credits at not than two sittings including English Language and Mathematics to be able to proceed to the tertiary level of the education system.

Basic Concepts of Education Policy at Secondary level of Education

Policy is an official prescription promulgated the authority to guide the attainment of goals. Education policy is binding guideline which describe and prescribe the objectives and strategies for the systematic of the business of education. Education policy entails specific goals, programmes and activities set by Governments on education for the attainment of education needs of the citizenry for economic growth and national development. Policy on education means Governments decisions on how actions on education can be carried out at different levels of educational system so as to improve the standard and performances in the education practice (Jumare, 2015).

Features of Policy in Education at secondary school of Education

There are specific features of policy in education as outlined by Jumare (2015) as follows

1. It involves actors (policy makers) and executers (policy implementers)
2. Most policy are in the form of summary statements of government line of action
3. Education policies are statutory functions of the government (control of education)
4. Education policies are futuristic in nature
5. Policy changes as needs of the society changes (policy is always dynamic)

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6. Most policies are made by the government

Sources of Education Policy at secondary school level of Education

Policy in education has different sources some of which are as follows:

1. Political leaders: Political leaders initiate and formulate education policies as captured by their political party's manifestos. For example, the Universal Primary Education (UPE) in 1955 in the Western Region and Universal Basic Education (UBE) in 1999/2000 and 6-3-3-4 system.
2. Legislative Arm of Government: The law-making body as an independent arm of government could also formulate policies that has to do education
3. Commission of Enquiry: Reports from Commission set by Government look for the needs and agitations of the populace, recommendations could be used to formulate education policies.
4. Educational Administrators and Planners: These are experts and professional in educational administration. Researchers and findings carried out by them became source of government policy in education. For example, the Curriculum Conference in 1977 (Jumare, 2015).

Types of Education Policy at secondary school level of Education

Many scholars have classified different types of education policies. Classification depends on the background and orientation of such scholars they are follows:

1. Distributive policy: This involves allocating or sharing of government resources to a particular group of population; states, regions and or individuals. This in education is always manifested in the process of admission into Nigerian universities as quota system, scholarships/fellowship school location and other government programmes in education.
2. Redistributive Policy: This policy entails change in allocating, sharing and distribution of resources or program formular. Okeke in Jumare (2015) sees this policy as policy equilibrium. This policy involves balance distribution of resources between areas that have and those that are lacking. For example, Jonathan administration in 2012 promised to established federal university in each of the 36 states of the federation.
3. Constituent Policy: This involves policies formulated for the use of a particular area, state or region. Universal Primary Education (UPE) in the Western region in 1955 and Almajiri system school in the Northern part of the country are good examples of this policy.
4. Regulatory Policy: This refers to a policy that involves regulating and controlling government agencies to fulfil the needs and yearnings of the citizenry. For example, National Universities Commission (NUC), National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) and National Board for Technical Education (NBTE).

Importance of Education Policy at Secondary level of education

Nwangu in Jumare (2015) states the importance of education policy as follows:

1. Policy statements are designed to guide implementation of education programmes and activities.
2. Policy provides the form and strategies on how the implementation of a given programme whether the desired result is being achieved for future development.
3. Policies determine the direction of future development of education program.
4. Administration of a program through policies confirm confidence on the personnel and education managers.
5. Policies help management in decision making and also assume continuity.
6. Policies give confidence to all stakeholders (in education) because there is something to guide decision making process.

Policy making process at secondary level of education

There are three variables in the public policy making process especially at the secondary level of education they are INPUT, CONVERSION and OUT PUT. Input consists of demands and support from the government. Not all demands made become policy agenda. There is also what is referred to as gate-keepers who select issues to be placed on the agenda. What informs their decision are the moral values of the people and the availability of economic resources to implement the policy. After the selection the agenda is forwarded to the institution responsible for making the policy (Ujo, 2011). Manga (2015) stated that policy making process is an organized activity that should be done in logical stages. The following constitute the steps in policy making process at secondary level of education:

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Step I: Problem identification: It must be as serious contemporary problem affecting the public

Step II: Problem Analysis: It must be broken down to establish its genesis, scope and implication

Step III: Formulation of strategies: Various alternatives for solving the problems are formulated.

Step IV: Selection of strategy: The best strategy is to select after considering the relative advantage and disadvantages of each.

Step V: Implementation: This involves putting into practice or action the selected strategies.

Step VI: Evaluation: The impact of the policy is assessed to determine areas of strengths and weaknesses.

Step VII: Policy Revision and adaptation: It is revised to correct mistakes and adopted to make it binding.

The National Policy on Education at secondary level of education

The National Policy on education is a document published by the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The Educational Research Council to serve as official guidelines to govern the educational system at all levels. The National policy on education gives the objectives and strategies to be pursued at national level as a whole. It also specifically provides guidelines on Early childhood/pre-primary education, Basic education, secondary education, mass literacy, Adult and non-formal education, science technical and vocational education, tertiary education, Open and distance education, special education, educational services, planning, administration and supervision of education as well as financing of education. A nation's policy on education is government way of realizing that part of the national goals that can be achieved education as a tool. No policy on education can be formulated without first identifying the overall philosophy and goals of the nation. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) the overall philosophy of Nigeria is to:

1. Live in Unity and harmony as one indivisible, democratic and sovereignty nation founded on the principles of freedom, equality and justice.
2. Personate inter-African solidarity and world peace through understanding. The five known National Goals of Nigeria which have endorse as the necessary foundation for the national policy on education are the building of:
 3. A free and democratic society
 4. A just and egalitarian society
 5. A united and self-reliant nation
 6. A great and dynamic economy
 7. A land full of bright opportunity for all citizens

Nigeria's Philosophy of education theories is based on:

1. Developing individual into a sound and effective citizen
2. Full integration of the individual into the community
3. Provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens at all levels from primary to university (Manga, 2015)

Policy Implementation at secondary level of education

Policy implementation is the process of putting a policy into action. Anderson in Ujo (2011) defined public policy implementation as "whatever is done to carry a law into effect, to apply it to a target population to achieve its goals". Anderson further asserted that the study of public policy implementation is concerned with the agencies and officials they employ and the political support and the opposition that they may encounter. Rushefsky (2007) described public policy implementation as the carrying out or execution of a programme that has been adopted by legislator or by executive or judicial order.

Characteristics of a good education Policy at secondary level of education

Manga (2015) asserted that, a good education policy at secondary level of education should have the following certain features:

1. Desirability: the policy must be desired by the people to whom it is made. It must not be forcefully imposed on people.
2. Clarity: A good policy must be stated in a very clear and understandable language to ease interpretation.
3. Relevance: A good policy must be relevant to the social, cultural and educational needs of the people.
4. Comprehensiveness: A good policy must contain detailed information on its objectives methods procedures and standard to be pursued.
5. Enforcement: A good policy must be one that is enforceable with punishment for violators
6. Flexibility: A good policy must make room for amendment and changes when circumstances require it.

Challenges of Secondary School Education in Nigeria

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It is not a gainsaying that secondary education is unique in the educational development of a child, being the link between primary and tertiary education. The knowledge, skills, values, and traits which a child acquires at this stage will complement those acquired at the primary level and when these are combined will prepare such child for tertiary education. In spite of the role of secondary education, (Ajayi, 2004) reported that it is riddled with crises of various dimensions and magnitude all of which combine to suggest that it is at crossroad. An examination of secondary education in Nigeria reveals the following challenges that are plaguing it and undermining the achievement of its objectives.

1. **Inadequate and low-Quality Teachers Inadequate staffing:** One of the reasons for the low level of quality assurance in Nigerian secondary schools is a severe shortage of teaching staff.
2. **Under funding:** One of the greatest challenges that appears to face Nigerian secondary schools is that of under-funding. Finance is so crucial to any organization that it continues to dominate discussions on the state of secondary level education in Nigeria. Running the institution, therefore, requires significant investment in providing and maintaining a basic level of infrastructure – such as facilities, staff salaries, and residential housing. Secondary Schools in Nigeria have been supported largely by government in the past, but with the economic down-turn, these Secondary Schools have been grossly under-funded and this has invariably led to the quality being adversely affected. Some of these institutions are characterized by poor infrastructures, overcrowded classrooms, incessant strikes and student unrest.
3. **Enrolment Explosion:** This over enrolment has become a common feature in Nigerian universities. Many of the facilities on the ground are being overstretched. This development will surely affect the quality of Secondary Schools education in Nigeria, since excess enrolment usually leads to overcrowded classrooms, ineffective teaching and
4. **Poor Management:** The way and manner some of the Nigerian secondary schools are being managed by the some school administrators has also had a consequential effect on quality assurance in the secondary schools. For most of the secondary school administrators, management means little more than playing the role of “Caretaker”. This vital function has been largely reduced to the maintenance of the status quo. This unfortunate development significantly negates the concept of a secondary education, particularly in a developing country like Nigeria. It seems certain that as long as management continues to play this non-challant role, the quality assurance will continue to be jeopardized in the secondary schools (Ujo, 2011).

Educational Policies in Contemporary Nigeria

In Nigerian educational system, there are numerous policies geared to better the system, this paper will discuss some of these policies. Their role in achieving primary and secondary education objectives.

Establishment of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN)

The Council was established by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria Decree (Now act) 31 of 1993. Several decades of agitation by professional teachers and other stakeholders for the establishment of a regulatory agency led to the enactment of the Act. The council finally became operational by June, 2000.

Responsibilities of the TRCN

The Act that established the council in section 1 (1) charged it with the following responsibilities

1. Determining who are teachers for the purpose of this Act
2. Determining what standard of knowledge and skill are to be attained by persons seeking to become registered as teachers under this Act and raising those standards from time to time as circumstance may permit.
3. Securing in accordance with the provisions of this Act the establishment and maintenance of a register of teachers and the publication from time to time of the lists of those persons
4. Regulating and controlling the teaching profession in all its aspects and ramifications
5. Classifying from time to time members of the teaching profession according to their level of training and qualification
6. Performing through the council established under this Act the functions conferred on it by this Act. (TRCN Teachers Hand book, Revised Edition, 2005).

A brief historical of education policies formulation and implementation in Nigeria

According to Odiba and Igono (2014) certain historical antecedents have impact on how educational policies are formulated and implemented in Nigeria. The Lagos Colony, Southern and Northern protectorates were British Colonies which were amalgamated in 1914 and named Nigeria. The Territory remained a British colony till 1960 when it attained independence. Nigeria has witnessed several educational reforms which started at pre-independence. It was to the credit of Nigerians agitators

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for self-rule that led the British colonial rulers to change the educational system in operation in 1954 from 8-6-2-3 system 8year primary, 6year secondary, 2year higher school certificate and 3year university to a new system 6-5-2-3 that is 6year primary, 5year secondary school, 2year higher school certificate and 3year university. The change resulted in reducing the number of years at the primary and secondary school levels. Nigerians then were more concerned about education. The hope in the educational reforms continued to rekindle after independence. The freedom of self-rule Nigeria was enjoying had no match with educational progress.

In September 1969 there was a National Conference held in Lagos. Participants at the conference were eager to see Nigeria chart a new course in its educational system. Such a system they reasoned will empower the country towards the path of scientific and technological development. They criticized colonial education system as lacking in vitality and reference. The conference recommended changes in the system from 6-5-2-3 system to 6-3-3-4 system that is 6year primary, 3year junior secondary, 3year senior secondary and 4year university education. The recommended system is simply American system of education which Japan copied and succeeded. In 1977 a new document known as National Policy on Education came to stay

Problems of Policy Implementation at secondary level of education in Nigeria

Problems of policy Implementation in Nigeria are many that hampered the successful implementation of education policy in the country some of which are as follows:

1. **Frequent change of Government:** Frequent change of government has resulted in frequent change of policy. Every government of the day in Nigeria comes with new policy by ignoring the previous ones. Most of the policies were not fully implemented let alone being evaluated. Most of these changes were during the military regimes. For example, Universal Basic Education (UBE) which is still facing numerous challenges in preparing students to senior secondary school level.
2. **Inadequate dependable data:** Data refers to statistical information that are used for making decisions. Therefore, data gives insight into policy formation, implementation, and success or otherwise. Thus, most data in Nigeria especially on secondary level of education are grossly inadequate and or alliterated due to political reasons. This affects policy implementation and decisions.
3. **Inadequate involvement of education stakeholders in policy formulation:** Most policies in education especially on secondary level of education lack incorporation of implementers and other stakeholders at the formation stage. Such stakeholders could include teachers, parents, religious leaders, traditional leaders, students and non-governmental organizations. This becomes a setback since the implementers have no in its formation.
4. **Inadequate funding:** this serves as a major setback in many education policies. For example., the UPE in 1955 (Western Region), the UPE of 1976 and the current UBE of 1999 without adequate funds to run the program. Thus, the program remained only paper.
5. **Corruption and misplacement of priority:** Several cases have shown that the scarce funds dedicated for policy implementation were either stolen or diverted for self-aggrandizement. Many times, governors read budgetary allocation dedicated to education policies and programs but unfortunately the program will end there. While in some cases the funds are diverted to other government activities. In fact, due to self-interest within the education sector, funds are made more available in some of a program while other not provided. Owolahi in Jumare (2015),

Conclusion

The conclusion of the paper is that, the failure of educational policies in Nigeria has been traced to poor monitoring and implementation of educational policies. It was discovered that these problems are policy formulation vurrus policy implementation, poor budgetary allocation, logistic problems, Nigeria philosophy of education, frequent changes in government and policies, corruption, inadequate awareness, lack of data for planning, lack of adequate consultation of policy implementers at the planning stage, inadequate skill manpower, inadequate provision of human, materials, infrastructure and financial resources among others.

Recommendations

1. **Governments** at all levels should ensure continuity in the implementation and evaluation of education policies before embarking of formulating new ones.
2. Adequate and dependable data should be provided as data gives insight into policy formation, implementation, evaluation and success or otherwise.
3. All stakeholders should be included at the formation stage of education policies

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4. Adequate funds should be provided for the implementation and evaluation of education policies.
5. More efforts should be put to carve the menace of corruption in the implementation and evaluation of education policies.
6. Effective education policies evaluation mechanism should be put in place so as to ensure optimal result.

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